

PRIVATIVE FEATURES IN JAPANESE NOUN PHRASES

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to delve further the morphosyntactic structure of Noun Phrases in Japanese and to understand which privative features are at stake when it comes to render common nouns definite in an articleless language like Japanese. The advantage of privative features over, let's say, binary features, is that they bring into discussion a certain syntactic peculiarity in a linguistic phenomenon, and this feature can usually be analyzed as a characteristic behavior for definite mechanisms in Japanese. Different theories, models and approaches take different views on features should be analyzed but we will make use of a simple classification in which we show that articleless languages can express definiteness as well.

Keywords: Features, Syntax, Semantics, Japanese, Binary, Definiteness, Deep-Structure, Noun Phrase, Linguistics

1. Privative Features

In English, privative features are often made use for in order to explain for the particular linguistic behavior of certain grammatical items, which cannot be explained in any other fashion. Borer (2005) offers a detailed discussion of the issues presented in this and the previous chapter and explores the richness of the internal functional structure of the NP to relate this to particular types of noun phrases. Along the lines of Cheng and Sybesma (1999), she proposes that the functional structure of the noun phrase contains layers such as Classifier Phrase (CLP) and Quantity Phrase (#P), see (80). The distinction between mass nouns and count nouns lays at the foundation of the properties that trigger the projections. In this manner, they become privative as a method to distinguish between nouns in terms of countability: [DP [#P [CIP[NP]]]]

According to the author, the generation of mass. vs. count structures is triggered by CL and is determined by the plural, classifier and by the indefinite article. #P, which corresponds to the Number Phrase, is the issuing projection for all other determiners, including the definite article. The absence of CLP gives rise to mass interpretation, while the absence of #P gives rise to an uncountable interpretation, which makes the existence of classifiers syntactically driven through a specified criterion in English (Alexiadou, 2007:225)

1. a. [DP [NP salt]]
determinerless mass
- b. [DP [CLP [NP dogs]]] determinerless
plural
- c. [DP [#P [NP salt]]] quantity weak mass
- d. [DP [#P [CLP [NP dogs]]]] quantity weak plural
- e. [DP the_i [#P ti [NP salt]]] definite mass

As we have seen, features are a flexible, an abstract mechanism with the potential to fully describe definiteness in English. Accordingly, any model of grammar should look to exploit the power of the tools at its disposal and aim to avoid proposing additional theoretical objects when the existing set could complete the task. This mirrors the Maximise Minimal Means (MMM) acquisition model proposed by Biberauer (2011) in which the acquirer checks whether any

existing linguistic trigger in their grammar can capture a distinction before resorting to creating a new one. The featural model and the structural model are two alternative ways.

In English, as we saw above, gender variation reflecting sex is coded either in different

lexical items (*mare/horse*) (suppletion) or in forms like *actor/actress*, *lion/ lioness*, where the feminine form can be considered as derived from the masculine via suffixation. We previously noted that Ritter proposed gender to be on N in English because it is derivational. She also proposed that it is on Num in Romance languages. The reason is the high degree of productivity of this strategy in Romance Languages and Hebrew: whereas gender switching is productive and regular in them, it is constrained by other semantic features (*animacy, humanness*) in English which points out to the necessity of making use of privativity for Gender.

Conclusive cross-linguistic evidence can be rather encountered for the semantic category Number constituting a syntactic head, which projects a Number Phrase in English. Number is an interpretable feature on nouns (agreement also includes other modifiers of nouns), the values of which can be chosen. In contrast, there is little support for postulating a category Gender as a functional head in the syntax. Gender is predetermined on nouns, it is semantic, and, as a consequence, it is syntactically uninterpretable. Gender in general is fixed through in the lexicon, but the feature [*animate*] can fluctuate the value of gender (*policewoman*) It is the lexical entry of each noun and is to be learnt along with the noun itself. As gender is taken to be an inherent property of N, as we pointed out, GenP is taken to be more closely associated with N. We represent it as structural position, *Gen* placed right above N (also Ritter 1993: 799):

2. DP > NumP > GenP > NP

Gender is arguably, along with Number, one of the privative features for English, since it is not specified at the level of the Noun Phrase, but, unlike Japanese, which lacks it, can be marked for by different strategies by means of semantic reference. This observation is important since it helps us determine the reason why

English allows definite articles and Japanese does not. The distinction between mass nouns and count nouns lays at the foundation of the properties that trigger the projections. In this manner, they become privative as a method to distinguish between nouns in terms of countability: [DP [#P [CIP[NP]]]]. There are a few mechanism through which this is achieved:

3. a. Masculine only: for male human beings: *father, boy, king*
- b. Feminine only: for female human beings: *mother, girl, queen*
- c. Neuter only: inanimate objects: *cahir, tree, table*
- d. Certain words acting as sex-indicators: *girl-friend, boy-friend, policewoman*
- e. Bound morphemes indicating feminine gender: *empress, heroine, tigress*
- f. Different words used for indicating the gender: *gentleman, uncle, aunt*

To better understand this concept, we can easily bring into discussion the case of restrictive modifiers as presented in the following phrases: Payne & Huddleston's (2002) account for the NP structure is relatively comprehensive. Quirk *et al.* (1985), on the other hand, restrict those dependents to modifiers, and make a distinction regarding their position within the noun phrase (whether they precede or follow the head noun). Nevertheless, the authors bring into discussion the following modifiers: restrictive (e.g. *my taller brother*), non-restrictive (e.g. *my clingy cat*).

The head of a Noun Phrase denotes a class that contains a subclass, this category is usually created by dependents that we refer to as restrictive modifiers, whereas descriptive or non-restrictive determiners are those which instantiate the referent of the NP with regard to a peculiar characteristic they exhibit (De Monink, 2000).

Whether Gender can be treated as a privative feature in English or not is a task easily solved with the involvement of mass nouns. Mass nouns cannot be feminine or masculine, not even at a syntactic level. If they show restrictive behaviour as to the determiners they select, then we can argue that Gender indeed influences the internal structure of Noun Phrases in English and can account for the employment of definite and indefinite articles. One such selective behavior is the choice of determiners, where mass nouns cannot accept *many* but they do accept *much* in order to convey the idea of plurality:

4.

a) *many drama(s)	<i>much</i> drama
b) *many gas(s)	<i>much</i> gas
c) *many information(s)	<i>much</i> information

One may argue there are exceptions which come against this observation with the classification of hybrid nouns, where they can be both count and mass. However, we must note that the semantic overview is different, since such instances don't multiply the mass noun, but the count one where the reference is for the

subset of the whole sequence. In the first column, the noun denotes a more abstract entity, where in the second column we deal with physical entities.

5.
 - a) We need much more *chocolate*.
We need many more *chocolates*.
 - b) We need high-quality *paper*.
We need high-quality *papers*.
 - c) We don't need much *rope*.
We don't need many *ropes*.
 - d) There isn't much *discussion*.
There aren't many *discussions*.
 - e) There is *reason* for this.
There is a *reason* for this.
 - f) There is a lot of *difference*.
There are a lot of *differences*

More examples of hybrid nouns include detail, complexity, error, effort, shortage, exposure, change, variation, etc. (Gillon, 1999 etc.). Note that hybrid nouns are

abstract nouns, e.g. *discussion, reason, difference, war*. We can talk about the same objects with either the count or mass version of the same hybrid noun, contrary to what the Mapping Hypothesis predicts. We can cite some more examples of hybrid nouns from different authors:

- (6) a. John is drinking beer.
b. We've just ordered six beers.
- (7) I ordered a pizza, not a slice of pizza!
(Gillon 1999:57)
- (8) a. Kim produces sculpture.
b. Kim is producing a sculpture.
(Pelletier 2012:14)

There are also instances of canonically count nouns employed as mass NPs. Nonetheless, the same principle applies, where they become purely distinct NPs with a physical, clearly described semantic component, unlike usual mass nouns:

- (9) a. This salad contains a lot of *apple*.
b. John ate *two apples*.
- (10) a. Leslie has more *car* than garage.
b. He's got *woman* on his mind.
(Pelletier 2012:14)
- (11) a. Bill got a lot of *house* for \$100,000.
b. How much *floor* did you lay today?
(Gillon 1999:58)

The conclusion that emerges from here is that the mass-count dichotomy cannot be solely rooted in the semantic content and the syntactic properties of the noun phrase. Rather, it is more of a social convention and relies on language modifications. However, the mass-count distinction is strongly stored in the linguistic system, and such nouns have been long debated and, as a matter of fact, they represent a closed class of elements. Above all, the Mapping Hypothesis captures the overall tendency of a noun to shift the lexical indexation. More precisely, it points out to a systematic semantic shift moving around the two sides

of a hybrid noun. What we intended to prove here is that there are selective triggers at the syntactic level which prove that Gender can be treated as a privative feature for English, in the same manner as it happens for mass/count nouns. For this fact we can add the feature (+/-Gender) to NPs in English and this syntactic operation makes it more easily understandable the structure of definiteness in English and why it is conveyed by lexical items like articles.

Payne & Huddleston (2002: 451) employ coordination and modification as syntactic test meant to determine whether a double noun structure is a *composite nominal* NP (their notion for

such syntactic constructions) or a *compound noun*. This is also important to mention, since we deal with two non-definite nouns and it raises the problem of definiteness. Thus, the compound noun puts emphasis on the first element, whereas the composite nominal emphasizes the second (e.g. *'yellowjacket* vs. *yellow jacket*). However, they recognise the imperfect nature of such tests, given that there are cases of composite nominals with left-periphery focus (e.g. *'biology teacher*) and compounds with right periphery focus (e.g. *ice cream* for many speakers). As a consequence, these nominals prove that definiteness in English is not only a matter of articles. When the stress tests kick in, some sort of restriction is present as a syntactic movement.

Giegerich (2004, 2005) introduces the variability of stress paradigms based on a so called *split site model*, whereby double noun structures are syntactically motivated both in the syntax and in the lexicon. Focus paradigms are thus predicted for some double noun structures whereas there is the stress pattern varies when it comes to other categories of Noun Phrases. Accordingly, he discusses the contrast between [complement + head] structures which originate in the lexicon and are marked for left-periphery (e.g. *'bricklayer*), and [attribute + head] structures which originate in the syntax and pertain to the right-periphery (e.g. *wooden 'stove*). Those types of Noun Phrases do not represent anything new and are normally attributive constructions (e.g. *'orange juice*) and can emerge as the consequence of a process involving lexicalisation. Nonetheless, this process cannot be followed by a gradual loss of syntactic properties, since the double noun structure would appear as a common social hazardous phenomenon. Finally, analogy may also explain such stress variability, based on the fact that many N+N structures choose their stress pattern in analogy with combinations that have the same head, i.e., the rightward element:

(12) month □ 'Pride Month > 'Chinese Month, 'Finnish Month

(13) avenue □ Sixth Avenue > Stockholm Avenue

The collocation with *month* as the second item here shows leftward focus, whereas

combinations with *avenue* show rightward focus in the same identical environment. It results, as a matter of fact, that [attribute + head] structures show variability in terms of stress patterns. However, Plag (2006:43) considers that this variability cannot be

explained in terms of lexicalisation, asserting that "*what is considered the effect of lexicalization in some approaches [Giegerich 2004] would emerge naturally in an analogical system*". According to Warren, (1993:60), nominal modifiers usually exhibit singularity as a result of restrictive operations and they also lose their ability to be inflected (e.g. *magazine seller*). We encounter cases where the referential use/lexical entry form of the noun shows plural inflection (*trousers*) and they drop off this plural interpretation when acting as a determiner (*trouser washer*). Following this, Adams (1973:59) argues that in N+N structures the first elements must be considered as grammatically *neutral* and not marked for singular morphology, as long as it is shown that in certain occasion the *s* genitive and not the plural *s* that is lost (*pigtail* < *pig's tail*).

Tamm & Rosenbach (2005) draws the conclusion that plurality marking is often absent as a consequence of noun modifiers having reduced referentiality, which is observed in context dependent situation. They found that the dependent *Bush* in *the Bush Administration* was less likely to fall under the influence of an anaphor or cataphor, than in the case of a genitive like *Bush's Administration*, taking into consideration the contextual reference. This implied that the modifier *Bush* was less salient than in the case of a genitive. However, as Quirk *et al.* (1985:1334) show, the employment of attributive Noun Phrases (e.g. *funks committee*) is gradually increasing.

Collective nouns and proper names (institutions) act as bearers and as heads, and the focus usually shifts on the pluralized modifying noun, as in examples (14) and (14).

(14a) horror magazines dealer

(14b) pocket picker

In (14a) specificity triggers the plural interpretation because the noun is determined by an adjective, whereas in (14b) the singular form is at stake because we deal with general referentiality of a certain class of people. Taylor (2000:361) considers the pluralized form of nouns as *sports* in the double noun construction *sports commentator* acceptable as an exception maybe because those plural nouns are ingrained in the social acceptance of the notion and have acquired a homogenous semantic connotation that is hard to modify.

(15a) science - certain branch of a researching domain

(15b) sciences - denotation for a certain researching facility

We showed in this paragraph that double NPs are by nature nondefinite from a syntactic point a view. However, such assumption would be redundant, so many authors concluded that it is a matter of stress pattern or specification as to which of the noun is the real determiner. The conclusion is that a N+N construction is definite in the absence of definite articles.

5.2.1.1. Conclusions of this Section

In English, privative features can be brought into discussion with emphasis on Gender and Number as a method to illustrate that both of them yield contribution to the field of definiteness. Even though it places constraints on the kinds of operations that can be defined on features, as in Japanese, it was conceived so as to make the difference in terms of plural/singular and definite/indefinite more structural. As observed, the difference is usually marked lexically so privativity was conceived to provide a paradigm to allow Gender and Number to encompass the occurrence of articles. More precisely, privativity comes as a syntactic means to emphasize that definiteness in English is also a grammatical issue, not a hazardous item and its behavior is marked by the employment of articles. They play a huge role, unlike in Japanese, which is articleless and doesn't own methods to express Number and

Gender, such as we find in English.

There are different approaches to defining the category of number. Thus, some scholars believe that the category of number in English is restricted in its realization because of the dependent implicit grammatical meaning of *countability*. Whether we should speak about this grammatical category as a privative feature of English in order to prove that they contribute to the general structure of definite NPs, through the aid of articles, as opposed to Japanese, was shown by depicting a selective node in counting mass nouns. Nouns are divided into two major classes: count nouns, which refer to individuals, and mass nouns which refer to non-individuals. It means that individuality is marked with the formal feature [+count] or better [+Num] as in Hicks (2019:37)

Lexical Item

16.

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